

DISEASE BRIEF: Disease Y

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	Disease Y is a previously unseen and unknown disease of any animal species that can potentially spread among (other) animals and has severe clinical signs.
2	Regulatory status in the EU	Nott applicable
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	Unknown
4	Reservoir / main host	Unknown
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	Unknown
6	Vector-borne transmission	Unknown
7	Environmental transmission	Unknown
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Unknown
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Unknown
10	Disease indicators	Morbidity and/or mortality
11	a) Clinical signs	Unknown
12	b) Seroconversion	Unknown
13	c) Other disease indicators	Unknown
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	<p>Increased morbidity and mortality in one or more animal species</p> <p>Increased morbidity of groups of clinical signs (syndromes, such as reproductive nervous, respiratory, etc) or specific productive and reproductive failures (abortion, conception failure, reduced litters, etc) which cannot be attributable to any other disease (undiagnosed cases).</p>

15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	Post-mortem examination of animals and full diagnostic investigation. Following exclusion of known pathogens, additional diagnostic investigations using metagenomics, whole genome sequencing, etc. (this is also applicable for wastewater and effluents samples).
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	Reporting of morbidity and/or mortality in: - livestock from farmers to veterinary practitioners followed by a full diagnostic investigation - in companion animals (dogs and cats) and exotic animals by veterinary practices and university animal hospitals - wildlife by hunters and veterinarians Examination of effluents and wastewater especially from planes and ships

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD	Component name
Disease X	Human								Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope
Disease Y	Livestock								Detection of new infectious agent causing disease (Disease Y) in livestock
	Companion animals								Detection of new infectious agent causing disease (Disease Y) in companion animals
	Exotic animals								Detection of new infectious agent causing disease (Disease Y) in exotic animals
	Wildlife								Detection of new infectious agent causing disease (Disease Y) in wildlife
	Effluents and waste water								Detection of new infectious agent (Disease Y) in effluents and wastewater

17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<p>Surveillance in animals (various species): this surveillance relies on reporting of clinical cases and deaths, awareness campaigns among general public to report animals found dead as well as among practitioners and laboratories to further investigate unresolved diagnoses with metagenomics and whole genome sequencing.</p> <p>Surveillance of undiagnosed clinical syndromes or mortality can be performed through all other existing surveillance components which rely on monitoring and detection of productive and reproductive performance decreases, clinical signs, and/or mortality in the given animal groups. Undiagnosed/unexplained cases should be considered potential Disease Y suspicions, and subjected to monitoring and, when relevant, follow-up.</p> <p>Surveillance through sampling of effluents and wastewater might require additional resources. However, samples taken for other purposes (eg COVID-19, Monkeypox) could be used for investigations regarding so far unknown pathogens.</p>
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	Not applicable
19	References	
20	Additional comments	Note: It is important to assure a timely exchange and investigations of similar cases in other animal species and humans